

**ACTIVITIES OF ORGANIZATIONS THAT MANAGE HEALTH AND
PHARMACEUTICAL ACTIVITIES**

Mirkhoshimova Mokhirakhon

Department of business administration, School of business, Changwon National
University. E-mail. mokhira1995@gmail.com

Sae Woon Park

Changwon National University. E-mail. assw@changwon.ac.kr

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7207328>

Annotation: In this article, the organization of pharmaceutical work is discussed in order to carry out its activities successfully. It also includes the principles of health care organization and the procedures for monitoring pharmaceutical activity in medicine.

Keywords: Ministry of Health, medicine, pharmaceuticals, medicine, laboratory, microbiological research, pharmaco-toxicological research.

The Republic of Uzbekistan carried out Ministry of Health and pharmaceutical activities improvement works to its own specific management system having this system provides medical care and medicines to the population plays an important role in providing the population with the leadership of the health care system in the republic is to SSV being charged, the ministry mainly solves the following issues:

- the health of the population and, depending on it, the national economy, its improvement of defense activities and development of health care;
- an alternative for highly qualified and all its strata of the population organization of medical care;
- development of measures to protect public health and prevent diseases;
- motherhood and childhood protection;
- that the sanitary-epidemiological situation of the republic is good provide;
- medicines for the population and medical and professional institutions, antiviral and diagnostic tools, used in medicine and others provision of goods;
- based on state plans, medical and professional institutions and taking measures to develop the pharmacy system;
- developing scientific research in the field of medicine and pharmacy, increasing its effectiveness, keeping them healthy and pharmacy to take measures to protect in practice;
- training of medical and pharmacist personnel, improving their qualifications raising the theoretical and practical knowledge to a high level;

- health based on scientific management of work providing storage institutions with relevant highly qualified personnel, achieving high results in restoring population health;

A commission (college) was established under the ministry, and it The Board of the Ministry of Current Problems in the Health Care System tasked with solving it together with its members. Scientific, practical, clinical and discussion of epidemiological problems, based on their plan implementation, the results of scientific and practical work in medicine and pharmacy to stay in republican medicine and thereby maintain health. Ministry for the development of practical and scientific directions in the fiel. Medical Scientific Council of Scientists was established under it. This is the board the prominent large of the republic on the basis of the public scientists, they are scientific about medicine and pharmacy along with the development of the direction, keeping it healthy and pharmacy in practice they are engaged in maintenance work. In addition, treatment-prophylactic assistance is provided Department, General Directorate of Motherhood and Child Protection, State department of sanitary-epidemiological control, economy and funds.

The main department of quality control of tools and medical equipment, Medicine policy center and other health departments perform important tasks in the management of the republic. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 181 of May 25, 1995. Quality control of drugs and medical equipment of Ministry of Health. Drug expertise and standardization in the main department. State center, Pharmacopoeia, Pharmacology, New medical techniques Committees such as Drug Control Committee, Medicines and Medical. Department of registration of equipment and Pharmaceutical for control inspection is available. State center of examination and standardization of medicines under:

- carrying out vaccines, serums and microbiological studies laboratory;
- quality control and standardization laboratory of medicines;
- medical equipment quality control laboratory;
- laboratory of pharmaco-toxicological research;
- a scientific methodical and information department was established.

The main tasks of the General Directorate are as follows:

- Produced in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan and controls the quality of imported drugs;
- quality of medicines between consumers and suppliers there are misunderstandings, disagreements and arguments about the issue. In the case of

the last, conducting an arbitration analysis of the quality of drugs gives a final conclusion;

- Medicines bought and brought to the Republic of Uzbekistan from abroad from State registration of means and medical supplies first, it controls the quality of the connection from all sides.

Save recipes. Recipes in special safes or metal stored in cabinets. Given for used drugs recipes are recorded, printed, and corded by month and year should be stored in special safes Shelf life of recipes:

Preferential drugs - 3 years.

Narcotics and psychotropic substances - 5 years.

Powerful and toxic drugs - apomorphine hydrochloride, atropine sulfate, homatropine hydrobromide, dicaine, silver nitrate, paxicarpine hydroiodide, ethyl- alcohol, anabolic hormones – 1 year. Expired prescriptions by commission will be destroyed based on the document. Hormones with an anabolic effect, including steroid hormones, tranquilizers, antidepressants, neuroleptics, 8-oxyquinoline

to prescriptions for stored medications and antihistamines. The stamp "Medication issued" is printed. New to get them again prescription is required. The quality of drugs prepared in the pharmacy is standard compliance with the requirements is one of the most urgent issues. Achieving this one of the possible ways is the quality of prepared medicines consists of provision and control. This is an arrangement types of drugs prepared and packaged in pharmacy institutions quality assessment and acceptable deviation standards and is used as a guideline in pharmacy institutions. Carrying out quality control of medicines in pharmacies control-analytical rooms will be organized to go. Control is analytical there are analytical tables in the rooms, they are equipped in the necessary order a must In front of the tables there are turntables and barbells on them, barbells will have the necessary reagents. Burettes and necessary on the tables solutions must stand. In addition, the state pharmacopoeia the latest edition and other regulatory documents must be included.

References:

1. Abdurakhmonov, J. U. Research of the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan and prospects of its development / J. U. Abdurakhmonov O. M. Voronina // Topical issues of new drugs development : abstracts of XXIV international scientific and practical conference of young scientists and student, April 20, 2017. - Kh., 2017. - Vol. 2. - P. 193-194.
2. VAYTON (2019). Pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan. [online] Slideshare.net. Available at:

<https://www.slideshare.net/vaytonbrandcapital/pharmaceutical-market-of-uzbekistan> [Accessed 14 Oct. 2019].

3. Akihiro Hashimoto, Shoko Haneda Measuring the change in R&D efficiency of the Japanese pharmaceutical industry / Research Policy 37 (2008) 1829–1836
4. Honjo, Y., Haneda, S.: R&D evaluation of Japanese pharmaceutical firms using DEA. J. Sci. Policy Res. Manag. 13, 96–105 (1998)).
5. Taewoo Youa,*, Xiaoying Chenb and Mark E. Holder Efficiency and its determinants in pharmaceutical industries: ownership, R&D and scale economy Applied Economics, 2010, 42, 2217–2241
6. Mao, Y., Li, J., Liu, Y.: Evaluating business performance of China's pharmaceutical companies based on data envelopment analysis. Stud. Ethno Med. 8, 51–60 (2014)